

Multi-objective optimization for a strategic ATM network redesign problem

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Abstract

During the last decades, the banking industry has been facing multiple challenges, from changes in regulations and legal systems, to the irruption of new technologies. A constant adaptation to the rapidly changing business ecosystem is therefore required. This paper deals with one type of efficiency improvement that is required from traditional banking operations as a result of the current shift in the industry towards more use of technology. That is, we deal with the decision-making process related to the redesign of existing ATM networks, which is currently being considered by many banks worldwide. This redesign is mainly a consequence of an increased use of electronic payment methods and card transactions, which have made the demand for cash decrease significantly. We describe a multi-objective mathematical programming model to be used as a tool when making strategic decisions regarding the bank ATM network redesign. Total costs and the coverage of customers and turnover are considered as conflicting performance attributes and analyzed through several multi-criteria techniques, namely the weighted sum and Tchebycheff methods and Archimedean goal programming. Among other insights, the results on a realistic case study show that the potential for cost reductions is high and that the consideration of both customer coverage and turnover coverage is crucial for the performance of the network.

Keywords: multi-criteria, banking, mathematical programming, strategic planning.

1 Introduction

The global banking industry, and especially the European, is starting to face a decreasing trend in their Automated Teller Machine (ATM) use. People's reduced use of cash in payments is one

of several factors that are contributing to cash redundancy and reduced profitability for ATMs (Finans Norge, 2015). For example, the number of money withdrawals from Norwegian domestic ATMs was reduced in 2013 by approximately 9 % from the year before and almost 35 % over the last decade (Norges Bank, 2013). The profitability of ATMs is also decreasing as a result of lower fees, mainly due to the increased use of electronic payment methods and card transactions. The current trend in the industry is a shift towards more use of technology, specifically related to Internet and mobile banking. The CEOs of Norwegian savings banks regard operating costs to be an important factor in the current structural changes (KPMG, 2014). Combined with investments in better technological solutions and related infrastructure, this implies that the operating costs of traditional banking operations, including ATMs, need to be reduced. This paper is focused on the design and analysis of a mathematical model to aid the decision-making process when redesigning an existing ATM network with the purpose of reducing its costs.

In particular, we approach a real strategic (with long-term effects greater than one year) location problem faced by large financial institutions in Norway, that see significant potential for cost reductions by optimization of their ATM network. As customer service is the primary purpose of the ATM network, the conflicting objectives of cost reductions and different forms of coverage are evaluated, the main issue being to quantify the effect of terminating/relocating ATMs in terms of customer behavior. As a consequence of this, the proposed model is based on the costs of operating an ATM and the expected loss or gain of sales because of termination or re-location.

The problem studied can be seen as a facility location problem where each ATM in the network is an independent facility supposed to meet a set of customers demand for cash. However, traditional facility location problems usually consider larger and more complex facilities than an ATM, which is essentially a storage, making traditional facility location approaches unsuitable for this problem.

For a good review over strategic facility location, the reader is referred to Owen and Daskin (1998). Additionally, Snyder (2006) provided a good review on facility location under uncertainty. However, the problem in this report seems not to have been studied before. Although there is existing literature addressing some ATM location problems, they usually focus on how an optimal ATM network should look like, without considering an existing ATM network. Furthermore, they are mostly focusing on coverage, while disregarding or downplaying the costs of having an ATM network. This may be a result of ATMs being significantly cheaper in operation than the operation of bank branches, and could also be the reason why it is not until recently that the trend is to reduce the number of ATMs. Due to this, it is reasonable that the literature up until now has been focusing on designing networks with high coverage. As such, the model proposed in this paper differs from other models for ATM location in the literature.

Wang et al. (2002) give an example of a facility location problem with stochastic demands applied to an ATM network. The objective is to minimize the customer's total waiting and travelling cost and the only financial considerations are an upper bound on the number of facilities deployed. Because of the complexity involved, the problem is solved heuristically.

Aldajani and Alfares (2009) propose a mathematical model for minimizing the total number of ATMs used to cover all customer demands in an enclosed geographical area. Here, arbitrary

demand patterns are considered and compared against the supply an ATM can generate. The generation of supply to each point with demand is based upon how supply degrades from a given location. Again, the problem is solved by using heuristics.

In Alhaffa and Abdulal (2011), the premise is that the location of ATMs is one of the most important criteria in choosing a financial institution. As such, they regard ATMs as an offensive marketing measure used to attract new customers, not merely as a defensive marketing measure as we do. They consider dual objectives, maximizing the covering proportion while using as few ATMs as possible. Three heuristics are presented for the problem. Some literature focuses on the use of geographic information systems together with optimization techniques, such as Mimis (2012) and Wambugu (2001).

Recently, Genevois et al. (2015) highlight the importance of considering together the location of ATMs and the cash management problem. In this paper, they review and discuss relevant previous works focused on these two related problems. Alternatively, Bilginol et al. (2015) analyze the impact of different factors on the ATM location problem through canonical correlation and ordinary least squares regression analysis. Some key factors that they indicate as relevant for ATM location are the population distribution, the location of points of interest and rival information.

The main contribution of the paper is a multi-objective linear integer programming model for a new strategic location problem of redesigning an existing ATM network. This model is actually motivated by the real case of a bank operating in Norway. Using the information provided by the bank, we build a realistic case study to test the proposed model. This case study is another interesting contribution of the paper, since it is created from real data and could be used to evaluate different mathematical models and/or business strategies. Furthermore, based on this case study, we analyze different multi-objective solution methods and provide extensive computational results illustrating the relation between the costs of operating the ATM network and different coverages. These results show that the potential for cost reductions is high, and that the value of coverage is of great importance to optimal solutions.

The paper is organized as follows. The approached problem is described in detail in Section 2. The proposed mathematical model is presented in Section 3. The multi-objective techniques used to solve the model are described in Section 4. Section 5 is devoted to data analysis and instance generation. An extensive computational study is developed in Section 6, and Section 7 presents our concluding remarks.

2 Problem description

The problem studied in this paper concerns finding the optimal ATM network configuration during a certain planning horizon given an existing network at the beginning. The ATMs at existing locations can either be kept operational, closed down, or relocated to another location. There might also arise a need to replace some ATMs throughout the planning horizon to keep the locations in operation. Furthermore, new ATM locations can be opened up throughout the planning horizon to improve the ATM network design. The planning is on a strategic level, which

implies a time horizon over several years (Simchi-Levi and Kaminsky, 2008). Other automat types, like deposit and change machines, and the bank's overnight safe service are not considered.

The network consists of both ATMs located at a bank office and freestanding ATMs. The current locations of the ATMs are given, and each ATM is assigned to a market area according to its geographical location. Since the bank needs to keep its customers' deposits available in cash, there is a lower limit on the number of ATMs that must be located in each market area.

Although ATM operation is believed to be more efficient than distributing money manually over the counter, the ATM operation is still a large expense for the bank. As such, the ATM operation can be regarded as a public service where the primary function is to be a service to the bank's customers. Furthermore, the loss of a service can lead to lower customer satisfaction, which subsequently might lead to a loss of customers.

The customer's experience regarding the ATM network can be split into several factors, but the main factors are the coverage and the individual service level. As a result, the problem we are considering in this paper is primarily based on geographical coverage, measured as the distance to the nearest open ATM location, but coverage of forecasted turnover is considered as well.

We consider multiple ATM locations, where each location may either be the location of an existing ATM or a possible new location. Each location is faced by the decision to operate or not in each time period. On the one hand, if an operating ATM is closed down, the decommissioning is permanent. On the other hand, to keep a location in operation, there might be a need to install a brand new or relocated ATM during the planning horizon. A newly installed ATM has an expected service life, but a specific ATM may be in operation for a longer or shorter time period than this, as the expected service life can be seen as the average time in service of all ATMs. A comparison of each ATM's individual age against the expected service life is usually performed, and depending upon the length of the planning horizon and the ATM network in question, there might be a need to do several changes at each location to keep it in operation.

If an ATM is relocated, the ATM can either be moved directly from one location to another, or stored for some time and then installed at another location. For an ATM to be a candidate for relocation, its age cannot exceed a maximal relocation age. However, since an ATM is not in use when stored, the storage is assumed to have no effect on its service life. A maximal storage time is enforced, as long time storage may make the ATM obsolete due to new technology.

Opening, terminating and relocating are all decisions that, when made, can be executed within a relatively short time. The changes in the network are therefore thought of as executed instantly in either the beginning or the end of a time period, with no downtime of the ATM.

Even though the primary function of an ATM is to be a service to the customers, they can also generate some revenues. These revenues may come from own customers (even though most of them usually do not pay any fees), from the inter bank fee (which is charged every time a customer from another bank firm is withdrawing cash), or from international customers (which are usually regulated through an external company).

Regarding ATM costs, they can be divided into investment costs and operating costs. The

investment costs are related to changes in the network (installation, termination and relocation) and the replacement of ATMs at the end of their service life. Even though the total cost related to termination differs from one location to the next, it is simplified into a one-time fixed cost in this problem. The used ATM is assumed as waste with no salvage value unless it is relocated. The cost of opening a new ATM, relocating an existing ATM and replacing an old ATM are treated as fixed costs. If a removed ATM is stored, this incurs a fixed storage cost. However, if the ATM is relocated directly within the same time period this incurs no storage cost, and the cost of disassembling and installation at the next location is no higher than the cost of only disassembling. The operating costs can be divided into four cost elements: Facility costs, financial capital costs, service costs, and value handling costs. Facility costs are costs associated with the physical location of the ATM. The financial capital cost is related to an opportunity cost. Service costs are associated to the maintenance of each ATM and are assumed to be fixed service fees paid per month and per ATM. Finally, the value handling costs are transportation costs and cash handling costs.

In short, the problem considered is how to find an optimal, or at least good, balance between total operating and investment costs for the ATM network and customer service provided by the ATM network in the form of coverage. This problem can be regarded as an uncapacitated location problem, as the number of customers each ATM can service is so large that a single ATM is sufficient for any location. The only exception to this is ATMs located in densely populated areas, where the visiting rate can be so high that queues may be forming. However, this is not taken into account in this problem, although it might lead to a loss of customers. The reasoning behind this is that ATM operation in general is not a profitable business (Jansson, 2011), and that today's coverage seems more than adequate. Therefore, any lost sales due to insufficient capacity are assumed to have a negligible influence on the bank's profit.

3 Mathematical programming model

This section presents a mathematical programming model describing the problem introduced earlier. The model is tailored for the real problem considered, but an effort is made in order to make the formulation as general as possible. The model may, with small modifications, also be used for similar types of facility networks, such as vending machines, fast-food outlets, and gasoline stations. In this sense, the addition of the possibility to relocate a facility may be of special interest as a way to optimize the resources available in the network, where resources can be interpreted as the physical facility or the capital, inventories, equipment, manual labour, knowledge, and skills at that location.

Time is discretized, assuming that any strategic decision occurs at the beginning of the corresponding time period and the storage and age of each ATM are calculated at the end of each time period. Furthermore, it is assumed that it is beneficial to install a new ATM as late as possible at existing locations. This implies that it is only possible to install a new ATM at an existing location in the planned replacement period and all feasible consecutive time periods with a time increment of the expected service life of an ATM. In addition, a relocation is not allowed for new locations during the first time period. Besides, if an ATM is closed down, the demand covered

by this ATM is assumed to be lost, and not transferred to other ATMs belonging to the bank.

It is desired to make as few changes in the network as possible, so no more than one relocation per ATM is allowed. In addition, it is always beneficial to postpone the installation of a new ATM at an existing location in this situation. Furthermore, as it usually happens in reality, we also assume that the planning horizon is shorter than the maximum relocation age plus one. These assumptions make it unnecessary to introduce variables to keep track of the ATMs age, simplifying the model significantly.

The main notation used in the description of the model is introduced in Section 3.1. It is based on the use of lower case letters to represent variables and subscripts, capital letters to represent parameters and sets and superscripts to define mnemonic composite parameters and sets. To reduce the size of the model, the variables are defined for as few combinations of subscripts as possible. The cost and revenue parameters are discounted to the beginning of the time horizon. In Section 3.2 we present the constraints of the model, while the multi-objective function is described in Section 3.3. Finally, we discuss some improvements of the model in Section 3.4.

3.1 Notation, parameters and variables of the model

Indices

- a - Market area
- i, j - ATM location
- m - demand node
- t, p - time periods
- k - covering criterion

Sets

- \mathcal{A} - Set of market areas
- \mathcal{I} - Set of all ATM locations, both existing and possible new locations
- \mathcal{I}_a^A - Set of all ATM locations that belongs to market area a ($\mathcal{I}_a^A \subset \mathcal{I}$)
- \mathcal{I}^E - Set of locations with existing ATMs in the beginning of the planning horizon ($\mathcal{I}^E \subset \mathcal{I}$)
- \mathcal{I}^N - Set of new ATM locations without an existing ATM, ($\mathcal{I}^N \subset \mathcal{I}$) and ($\mathcal{I}^N = \mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{I}^E$)
- \mathcal{I}_{mk}^C - Set of ATM locations that are within a distance D_k^C of demand node m
- \mathcal{M} - Set of demand nodes
- \mathcal{T} - Set of time periods
- \mathcal{K} - Set of covering criteria

Revenue and cost parameters

R_{it}	- Revenue generated by the ATM on location i in time period t	[NOK]
C_{it}^{TO}	- Total cost for operating an ATM at location i in time period t , excluding depreciation costs	[NOK]
C_t^{TDN}	- Cost of new ATM given installation in time period t	
C_t^T	- Fixed cost of terminating an ATM in time period t	[NOK]
C_t^R	- Fixed cost of relocating an ATM in time period t	[NOK]
C_t^I	- Fixed cost of installing a new ATM in time period t	[NOK]
C^π	- Total cost of operating the existing network throughout the planning horizon	[NOK]

Covering parameters

I_{at}^A	- Minimum number of open ATMs in market area a in time period t	[-]
D_k^C	- Maximal distance from a demand node to an ATM in covering criterion k	[m]
N_m^C	- Number of customers in demand node m	[-]
N^{TOT}	- Total number of customers	[-]
P_{tk}^C	- Minimum covered proportion according to covering criterion k in time period t	[-]
P_t^T	- Minimum proportion of turnover that must be covered by the network in time period t	[-]
O_{it}	- Forecasted turnover in ATM at location i in time period t	[NOK]
O_t^T	- Total forecasted turnover in time period t	[NOK]
P^0	- Current covering proportion of the existing network	[-]

Time parameters

T_i^{ATM}	- Time in service of the ATM at location i in the beginning of the planning horizon	[months]
T_i^N	- Planned time period for replacing the ATM at location i ($i \in \mathcal{I}^E$)	[months]
\bar{T}^R	- Maximum service time for an ATM for it to be allowed to relocate	[months]
\bar{T}^{SL}	- Maximum service life of an ATM	[months]
\bar{T}^S	- Maximum storage time	[months]

Other parameters

\bar{S}	- Maximum number of ATMs allowed to be stored	[-]
S^0	- Inventory of ATMs in the beginning of the planning horizon	[-]

Variables

- x_{it} - 1 if an ATM is open at location i in period t , 0 otherwise
- y_{it} - 1 if a new ATM is installed at location i in the beginning of period t , 0 otherwise
($t = T_i^N, T_i^N + T^{SL}, \dots, T_i^N + nT^{SL} \leq |\mathcal{T}|$ if $i \in \mathcal{I}^E$)
- z_{imt} - 1 if ATM location i is covering demand node m in period t , 0 otherwise
- d_{mtk} - 1 if demand node m is not covered by any operating ATM in time period t according to covering criterion k , 0 otherwise
- w_{ijtp} - 1 if the ATM at location i is relocated to location j , where the ATM will be removed in the beginning of time period t and installed in the beginning of time period p , 0 otherwise ($i \neq j, t \leq p, t \neq T_i^N$ if $i \in \mathcal{I}^E, p - t \leq \bar{T}^S, t \neq T_i^N$ and $t, p > 1$ if $i \in \mathcal{I}^N$)
- s_t - Number of ATMs in storage in the end of time period t

Figure 1: Illustration of how decision variables x_{it} , y_{it} and w_{ijtp} work

Figure 1 gives a graphical description of the behavior of the most important variables of the model: x_{it} , y_{it} and w_{ijtp} . The decision of whether to install a new ATM or not, controlled by y_{it} , is taken in the beginning of each time period. This can either be the installation of an ATM at a new location, or the replacement of an existing ATM because of its age. As an alternative to installing a new ATM at location i , an ATM from another open location j' can be relocated to location i . Then, this ATM will be removed from location j' in the beginning of time period p and installed at location i in time period t , as indicated in the figure. Location j' will always be closed down in the event of a relocation. If relocated, the ATM can be relocated directly in the same time period, i.e. $t = p$. Otherwise the ATM needs to be stored in order to be used later in the planning horizon. The variable controlling ATMs in storage, s_t , is not included in Figure 1 because it is not formulated explicitly for each location i . The variable x_{it} controls whether location i is open or not in time period t . If the ATM at location i is decommissioned or relocated in the beginning of time period t , x_{it} will be zero in time period t and all subsequent time periods.

Figure 2: Illustration of how variables d_{mtk} work: geographical coverage

Figure 3: General view of the structure of the model

Figure 2 illustrates the function of variables d_{mtk} . Here, d_{mt1} is equal to one because no ATM location is open within the primary service distance D_1^C of demand node m . At the same time, demand node m is covered within the secondary service distance, D_2^C , so both d_{mt2} and d_{mt3} are zero.

Additionally, Figure 3 provides a general view of the temporal structure of the model, highlighting the main information known at each time point, the decisions that must be made and its effect on the following time period, indicating the variables involved in each case.

3.2 Constraints of the model

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_a^A} x_{it} \geq \underline{I}_{at}, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (1)$$

$$x_{it} - z_{imt} \geq 0, \quad m \in \mathcal{M}, i \in \mathcal{I}_{m|\mathcal{K}}^C, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{mk}^C} z_{imt} + d_{mtk} \geq 1, \quad m \in \mathcal{M}, t \in \mathcal{T}, k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} N_m^C (1 - d_{mtk}) \geq P_{tk}^C \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} N_m^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^E} O_{it} x_{it} \geq P_t^T \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^E} O_{it}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5)$$

$$x_{i(t-1)} - x_{it} \geq 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}^E, t \in \mathcal{T} \mid t > 1 \quad (6)$$

$$x_{it} - y_{it} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}^E} w_{jitt} = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}^N, t = 1 \quad (7)$$

$$x_{it} - x_{i(t-1)} - y_{it} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{p=1}^t w_{jipt} \leq 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}^N, t \in \mathcal{T} \mid t > 1 \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} y_{it} \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}^N \quad (9)$$

$$x_{it} - y_{it} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{\tau=1}^t \sum_{p=1}^{\tau} w_{jipt} = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}^E, t = T_i^N \mid T_i^N \leq |\mathcal{T}| \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{p=t}^{|\mathcal{T}|} w_{ijtp} - x_{i(t-1)} \leq 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \mid t > 1 \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{p=1}^t w_{jipt} - x_{it} \leq 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12)$$

$$x_{it} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{p=t}^{|\mathcal{T}|} w_{ijtp} \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{p=t}^{|\mathcal{T}|} w_{ijtp} \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{T}} \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} w_{jitp} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} w_{ijtp} \right) \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{p=t}^{|\mathcal{T}|} (T_i^{ATM} + t - 1) w_{ijtp} \leq \bar{T}^R, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}^E, t \in \mathcal{T} \mid t < T_i^N \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}^E} \sum_{p=1}^t (T_j^{ATM} + p - 1) w_{ijpt} + \sum_{\tau=t}^{|\mathcal{T}|} (x_{i\tau} - (|\mathcal{T}| - \tau + 1)y_{i\tau}) \leq \bar{T}^{SL}, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \mid p < T_j^N \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{p=2}^{|\mathcal{T}|} w_{ijtp} + S^0 - s_t = 0, \quad t = 1 \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{\tau=1}^t \sum_{p=t+1}^{|\mathcal{T}|} w_{ij\tau p} - s_t = 0, \quad t \in \mathcal{T} \mid t > 1 \quad (19)$$

$$s_t \leq \bar{S}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (20)$$

$$x_{it} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (21)$$

$$y_{it} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \mid t = T_i^N, T_i^N + T^{SL}, \dots, T_i^N + nT^{SL} \leq |\mathcal{T}| \text{ if } i \in \mathcal{I}^E \quad (22)$$

$$z_{imt} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, m \in \mathcal{M}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (23)$$

$$d_{mtk} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad m \in \mathcal{M}, t \in \mathcal{T}, k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (24)$$

$$s_t \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \quad t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (25)$$

$$w_{ijtp} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}, p \in \mathcal{T} \mid i \neq j, \quad t \leq p, (p - t) \leq \bar{T}^S, t \neq T_i^N, t, p > 1 \text{ if } i \in \mathcal{I}^N. \quad (26)$$

Constraints (1) ensure that a lower limit on the number of ATMs located in each market area is satisfied during each time period. This lower limit might change throughout the planning horizon because of trends in customer behavior. Constraints (2) enforce that only open ATMs are allowed to cover the demand nodes, while constraints (3) are set covering constraints, where the slack d_{mtk} controls whether demand node m is covered according to covering criterion k or not.

The covering criteria $k \in \mathcal{K}$ are associated with monotonically increasing covering distances $D_1^C < D_2^C < \dots < D_{|\mathcal{K}|}^C$ which represent certain service distances relevant to the bank's customers. Similarly, at each time period t , each covering criterion $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is related to a minimum covered proportion P_{tk}^C , that represents a lower bound on the proportion of demand nodes that must be covered according to that criterion. These minimum proportions are monotonically increasing, i.e. $P_{t1}^C, \dots, P_{t|\mathcal{K}|}^C$. As a result, if a demand node is covered according to criterion k , it is automatically covered according to criteria $k + 1, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|$. In practice only two covering criteria are usually used, which are associated to what are called primary and secondary service distances. Constraints (4) ensure that at least a proportion P_{tk}^C of the customers are covered

according to covering criterion k in time period t . If the slack d_{mtk} is equal to one, demand node m is not covered by any ATM within service distance D_k^C and the population in demand node m does not count for covering criterion k in time period t .

In addition to geographical coverage, future turnover is also considered by the model. In order to guarantee a certain coverage, constraints (5) impose that a minimum proportion P_t^T of the forecasted turnover on the existing locations is covered at each period t .

Constraints (6) ensure that an existing ATM location must stay closed for all remaining time periods when decommissioned. If an ATM is opened at a new location i , constraints (7) and (8) make sure that either a new ATM or an ATM relocated from another location j is installed in the beginning of the first period location i is open. This gives the model the possibility to open up and close down ATMs at new locations several times during the planning horizon, which can be imposed by the inclusion of constraints (9).

Constraints (10) ensure that if an ATM that is currently operating was already working in the beginning of the planning horizon, it cannot be operating longer than T_i^N before it is replaced or closed down. The replacement can either be a new ATM or an ATM relocated from another location. In the event of a relocation, constraints (11) and (12) enforce that the arrival and destination nodes, respectively, are both open in the related time periods. Since the removal of an ATM is defined to occur in the beginning of time period t , constraints (11) guarantee that the ATM is open in the preceding time period. Similarly, constraints (12) ensure that an ATM can only be installed as long as the destination node is open in the time period of installation. As long as the cost of relocation, C^R , is larger than the termination cost, C^T , constraints (12) are not strictly necessary, because the model will never find it beneficial to relocate an ATM to a closed location. Constraints (13) make sure that a new ATM cannot be installed at a location where an ATM is removed. Furthermore, an ATM can physically only be relocated to one location in each time period, which is ensured by constraints (14).

Constraints (15) enforce that if an ATM is relocated from ATM location j to ATM location i , it cannot be relocated once more from ATM location i and to yet another ATM location j . Constraints (16) ensure that the age of a relocated ATM does not exceed the maximum relocation age, \bar{T}^R . These constraints are only applied to all existing ATM locations before their last time period for replacement, as relocating new ATMs installed during the planning horizon will always be allowed when $|\mathcal{T}| \leq \bar{T}^R + 1$. If an existing ATM is relocated, constraints (17) keep track of the ATM's age from its original location j , and the number of years in operation at its current location i . Constraints (17) also guarantee that the sum is less than the expected service life of an ATM, unless a brand new ATM is installed as well. If an ATM is relocated and not installed in the same time period as it is removed, a storage cost per time period stored is incurred. The inventory level in any given time period is given by constraints (18) and (19), and is limited to its maximum level in all time periods by constraints (20). Finally, the integrality conditions for the decision variables are given in (21)-(26).

3.3 Multi-objective function

Since the ATM network's primary function is to be a service to the bank's customers, we use a multi-objective function which, in addition to the cost, also includes the total geographical coverage and the total coverage of turnover to represent customer satisfaction.

$$\begin{aligned}
\min f_1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{s}) = & \frac{1}{C^\pi} \left[\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (C_{it}^{TO} - R_{it}) x_{it} \right. \\
& + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (C_t^{TDN} + C_t^I) y_{it} \\
& + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^E} C_1^T (1 - x_{i1}) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^E} \sum_{t=2}^{|\mathcal{T}|} C_t^T (x_{i(t-1)} - x_{it}) \\
& \left. + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} C_t^S s_t + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} C_{t-1}^R w_{ijt} \right], \tag{27}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\min f_2(\mathbf{d}) = \frac{1}{P^0} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{T}|} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}|} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \frac{N_m^C}{N^{TOT}} d_{mtk}, \tag{28}$$

$$\min f_3(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{T}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^E} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \frac{O_{it}}{O_t^T} (1 - x_{it}), \tag{29}$$

Objective function (27) represents the net present total costs to operate the ATM network given expected future revenues and operating costs. In order to make the costs relative to the current status of the network, f_1 is scaled by dividing by C^π . Each ATM generates both revenues and operating costs when operating, and the total operating loss for the network is given in first part of (27). Here, C_{it}^{TO} is the total operating costs, including all fixed and variable costs related to its operation. The total investment costs for new ATMs, including installation, is given in the second part, where the discounted investment cost is C_t^{TDN} and the discounted installation cost is C_t^I . If an ATM is closed down and removed in the first time period, a termination cost C^T is incurred, as given in the third part, while the total cost of terminations for the rest of the planning horizon is given in the fourth part. Storage costs are included in the fifth part and, finally, if an ATM is relocated directly from location i to location j within the same time period, a lump sum for the whole operation, C_t^R , is incurred. Objective function (28) is the average geographical coverage during the planning horizon for all covering criteria relative to the current covering proportion P^0 , and objective function (29) is the average coverage of future forecasted turnover.

3.4 Special ordered sets and elimination of constraints

The variables that control installation, y_{it} , and relocation, w_{ijt} , of ATMs, can only be non-zero at most once during the planning horizon, for each i and each pair of i and j , respectively. This makes them viable candidates to be modeled as part of a special ordered set of type one (SOS1).

An SOS1 is an ordered set of variables where at most one variable can have a non-zero value (Beale and Tomlin, 1970). Since at most one new ATM can be installed at location i , and the ATM at location i can only be relocated to location j at most once, explicit slack is added, as in (Nygreen et al., 1998). The addition of explicit slack, defined here as δ_i and δ_{ij} , respectively, is shown in constraints (30) and (31). Branching on SOS1 variables leads to more balanced search trees and can be more efficient than on binary variables if the variables can be ordered in some way, as discussed by Beale and Tomlin (1970). The explicit slack is added here as a mean to first branch on whether a new ATM should be installed or not and if the ATM should be relocated or not.

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} y_{it} + \delta_i = 1, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}^N \quad (30)$$

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{T}} w_{ijtp} + \delta_{ij} = 1, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{I} \quad (31)$$

Some preliminary experiments performed with the case study showed that the storage possibility of the model was not used, probably because the use of the storage option was not needed to perform a relocation. In all cases, direct relocations were always preferred, as they provided cheaper solutions. Taking this into account, the problem could be simplified by setting the allowable storage time to zero, which would allow the relaxation of constraints (18)-(20) and the elimination of the index p for variables w_{ijtp} .

When $|\mathcal{T}| + T^R \leq T^{SL}$, constraints (17) are also unnecessary. The earliest possible relocation of an ATM at its limit ($t = T^R$) is in the beginning of the first time period. In our computational experiments, the maximum expected service life for an ATM is ten years and the maximum relocation age is six years, thus the previous inequality is satisfied and there is no need for constraints (17).

4 Multi-objective techniques

To solve the multi-objective problem, we have applied several multi-objective methods: the weighted sum method, two different weighted linearized Tchebycheff methods, and Archimedean goal programming.

Let us assume that the problem we want to solve is formulated as follows:

$$\min \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = [f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_k(\mathbf{x})]^T \quad (32)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{x} \in S, \quad (33)$$

$$\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T, \quad (34)$$

where $f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_k(\mathbf{x})$ are the k objective functions, (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) are the n decision variables and $S \subseteq R^n$ is the solution space. We also use a vector \mathbf{w} of attribute weights, typically set such that $\sum_{i=1}^k w_i = 1$ and $\mathbf{w} > 0$.

4.1 Weighted sum method

The a priori weighted sum method can be described as follows (Marler and Arora, 2004):

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}} U = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i f_i(\mathbf{x}), \quad (35)$$

This is a particular case of the *global criterion method*, where all objective functions are combined into a single function. This is one of the simplest methods for solving multi-objective optimization problems and provides both a necessary and a sufficient condition for Pareto optimality.

4.2 Tchebycheff method

The weighted min-max method (Marler and Arora, 2004), also called the *weighted Tchebycheff* method, is formulated as

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}} U = \max_i \{w_i [f_i(\mathbf{x}) - f_i^0]\}, \quad (36)$$

where $f_i^0 = \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}} f_i(\mathbf{x})$ for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. The point $(f_1^0, f_2^0, \dots, f_k^0)$ is usually called the utopia point.

This method is often linearized as follows.

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}, \lambda} \lambda \quad (37)$$

$$\text{s.t. } w_i [f_i(\mathbf{x}) - f_i^0] - \lambda \leq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (38)$$

The increasing number of constraints in formulation (37) - (38) can increase the complexity of the problem (Marler and Arora, 2004), but it keeps the linearity as long as the original problem is linear. This method verifies a necessary condition for Pareto optimality (Miettinen, 1999), but could also produce weakly Pareto optimal solutions, not guaranteeing a sufficient condition for Pareto optimality. However, Kaliszewski (1987) shows that it is possible to modify equation (36) to alleviate the weakly Pareto optimal solutions. This is called the *modified weighted Tchebycheff* method and is formulated as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}} U = \max_i \left\{ w_i \left(f_i(\mathbf{x}) - f_i^0 + \rho \sum_{j=1}^k (f_j(\mathbf{x}) - f_j^0) \right) \right\} \quad (39)$$

where ρ is a small scalar. Minimizing (39) provides both a necessary and a sufficient condition for Pareto optimality for discrete problems and problems with only linear constraints (Kaliszewski, 1987). This equation can be linearized in a similar fashion as the linearization of the weighted Tchebycheff method shown in (37) - (38).

4.3 Archimedean goal programming

Goal programming (GP) was developed in the fifties and sixties with major contributions from Charnes et al. (1955) and Charnes et al. (1967). In goal programming, goals g_i are specified for each objective function $f_i(\mathbf{x})$ and their total deviation $\sum_{i=1}^k |d_i|$ is minimized, where d_i is the deviation from goal i . To model the absolute values, d_i must be split into a positive and a negative part such that $d_i = d_i^+ - d_i^-$, where $d_i^+, d_i^- \geq 0$ and $d_i^+ d_i^- = 0$. d_i^+ and d_i^- can be interpreted as the overachievement and underachievement of a goal, respectively.

The purpose of goal programming is to find the solution with the smallest deviation from the utopian solution (Andersson, 2000). To solve the problem proposed in this paper, we use what is called Archimedean goal programming (or *weighted goal programming*), which assigns weights to the deviation of each objective from its respective goal. This method is formulated in Charnes and Cooper (1977) as follows:

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^k w_i^+ d_i^+ + w_i^- d_i^- \quad (40)$$

$$\text{s.t. } f_i(\mathbf{x}) - d_i^+ + d_i^- = g_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k, \quad (41)$$

$$d_i^+, d_i^- \geq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k, \quad (42)$$

$$d_i^+ d_i^- = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k, \quad (43)$$

where $w_i^+, w_i^- \geq 0$ are representing the relative weights put on each deviation from goal i with value g_i . One drawback of this method is that there is no guarantee for a Pareto optimal solution. Besides, the need for additional variables and constraints can make the problem harder to solve. However, despite its problems, goal programming is a popular method used in a wide range of applications (Marler and Arora, 2004), mainly due to its flexibility and capability to include the preferences of the decision maker.

5 Data analysis and instance generation

This section describes how the instances to be solved in the computational study have been generated from the raw data available from different sources.

5.1 Geographic data

The coordinates for each ATM were retrieved from GoogleMaps with the use of each ATM's address. A distance matrix between all ATMs and all municipality centers in the region were constructed by the use of Google's API for GoogleMaps (Google). For most customers, a trip to the municipality center is necessary to withdraw cash, and one can assume that those customers are covered if an ATM is located in the municipality center.

5.2 Forecasting of future turnover

The estimated turnover for cash is forecasted by the use of a SARIMA(1,1,1)-model, following the Box-Jenkins methodology. We had monthly historical data from January 2010 to November 2014, leading to 59 data samples. As it could be expected from a data sample of this size, and as it was confirmed later by our experiments, a higher order model does not give better forecasts. Both the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) have been used to confirm this, indicating that a SARIMA(1,1,1)-model is sufficient. By using PP-plots and QQ-plots, we were also able to confirm that the residuals, i.e., the difference between the samples and the estimated function values follow a normal distribution. The forecast of turnover from the SARIMA(1,1,1)-model indicates, as expected, a non-stationary trend with high seasonality. The non-stationarity coincides with the existing trend of decreasing demand of cash withdrawals commented earlier.

5.3 Revenue and cost prognosis

The forecasts of future revenues and costs are based on historical data. However, when data are missing or not available individually for each ATM, the required information is indirectly forecasted with the use of other correlated factors.

Time varying data

Based on knowledge of the cost structure, both revenues and financial capital costs seem to be time varying and highly seasonal. Since no revenue and cost data for individual ATMs exist, all revenues and financial capital costs are assumed to be linearly correlated with the turnover. As such, both the revenue and financial capital forecasts are based on the forecast of turnover. Revenue data can only be extracted on a yearly basis, aggregated to a total number for all ATMs. As such, future revenues for each ATM are assumed to be linearly correlated with the future demand for money. This seems like a reasonable assumption, as it is likely that higher demand leads to higher revenues. However, this does not take into account regional and local differences and the fact that some ATMs offer foreign currency. As there is no empirical data available on the relation between relative revenue and the inclusion of foreign currency, there is no bias towards ATMs that include foreign currency, i.e. the same ratio is used for all ATMs. We observed revenue-turnover ratios of 0.92, 0.83, and 0.77 over the last three years preceding the study. Thus, we performed the estimation assuming a linear correlation between revenues and turnover and, due to the historical variation, we considered only the ratio of the last two years, leading to an average ratio of 0.80, which is the value used in the tests.

The financial cost data have a somewhat higher detailing level, with cost data available per month for each market area. This allows for better forecasts of the financial capital cost than for the revenues, although the detailing level is still lower than desired. The forecast procedure is similar to that of revenue forecasting, as the financial cost forecast is also based upon the future turnover forecast and a cost-turnover ratio (CT-ratio). However, as values are available on a more detailed level, the ratio estimation is also more detailed with individual ratios for each market area and each month. If the assumption that the turnover is linearly correlated with

the financial costs is valid, we should observe a relatively steady historical CT-ratio. However, as seen in Figure 4, this is not the case and, in fact, it seems like the CT-ratio is strongly seasonal. As such, an average ratio for each month and market area is estimated, shown in red in Figure 4. Again, the y-axis values are censored due to sensitive information and competitive considerations.

Figure 4: Cost-turnover ratio last three years

Fixed data

The rest of the operating and investment costs are assumed to be fixed and related to recent values or are obtained from qualified guesses made by experts. The reason for this is that, while both the revenues and the financial capital cost are clearly time-varying and seasonal, the other operating costs seem to either be fixed in time or have no clear trend. This implies that, while it is possible to give acceptable forecasts for the revenues and the financial capital cost, it is assumed to give no further insight to forecast the rest of the operating costs.

Historical data on value handling costs per location are provided by the bank. These costs include the transportation costs and cash handling costs for filling the ATMs with different types of bank notes. However, since the bank locations may have several types of automats and one visit might include more than one automat type, the value handling costs at each location are not easily broken down. Furthermore, the ATM might not be visited each time a location is visited. As such, the historical value handling costs per ATM must be estimated, and for this purpose, the value handling costs are defined as the potential savings per location if the ATM is closed down.

The historical potential savings for location i at time period t are calculated by comparing the visit rate for the ATM to the total visit rate for location i . If the ATM has a visit rate less than

or equal to the total number of visits, the potential savings are defined as the filling costs times the number of fillings. Otherwise, the potential savings due to a reduction in the total visits to location i are added as well. It is assumed that the decommissioning of the ATM at location i has no other effects, such as further savings as a result of also decommissioning other automat types. The future value handling costs are estimated by taking an average of the most recent values.

Data generation for new ATM locations

The generation of revenue and cost data for the new locations is performed on the basis of the forecasts for existing locations. We assume that all new operating ATM locations will have freestanding ATMs. Since there have been no new ATM locations for a long time, there exist no historical data that can be used to estimate the revenues and costs of operating new ATM at new locations. As such, all new ATM locations are treated equally and given the average revenues and total costs of all existing freestanding ATMs.

5.4 Generation of the base case

After several preliminary tests and a deep analysis of the available data, a realistic base case has been generated. The main data of the base case is presented in Table 1. Here, the limit on the minimum number of ATMs per market area is relatively low, while the covering proportion and covering distance are both fairly high. The maximum storage time is set to 2 months if storage of ATMs are allowed and zero otherwise.

Parameter	Value
Length of planning horizon, $ \mathcal{T} $	36 months
Number of covering criteria k	1
Service distance, D_k^C	1 km
Covering proportion, P_{tk}^C	93 %
Decrease in covering proportion	5 %
Discount rate	4 %
Maximum inventory, \bar{S}	2
Initial inventory, S^0	0
Service life, T^{SL}	120
Maximum relocation age, T^R	72
Maximum storage time, \bar{T}^S	0 (2)

Table 1: Main data of the base case

Since the costs are regarded by the bank as sensitive information, all data or results related to absolute costs are censored. Instead, values relative to the cost of the current operation are

reported, which are to be interpreted as proportions of the cost of the current operation. As a result, values less than 100 % indicate savings achieved with respect to the current operating cost: the smaller the value, the larger the saving.

6 Computational Study

This section presents an extensive computational study performed on the base case introduced in the previous section and some variations of it. Since the main objective of this work is to analyze the trade-off between costs and customer satisfaction, a wide range of computational experiments are performed to provide the best possible basis for decision-making. The mathematical model is written in Xpress Mosel Version 3.6.0 and implemented in FICO[®] Xpress Optimization Suite 7.7 on a computer with 64-bit Windows 7 Enterprise, Intel[®] Core[™] i7-3370 3.40 GHz CPU and 16.0 GB of RAM.

6.1 Cost optimization results

This section deals with the analysis of the results obtained by considering only the cost objective function (27) when solving the model. This analysis is focused on studying the underlying relationship between different elements of the problem, such as primary and secondary service distances, customer coverage, turnover, and ATM revenues.

6.1.1 Covering criteria

One interesting analysis consists of studying the effect of varying the primary (D_1^C) and the secondary (D_2^C) service distances, which are related to the first two covering criteria. For this purpose, Figure 5 shows how different potential savings can be achieved for varying combinations of D_1^C and D_2^C . The triangle shape of the figure is due to the fact that the secondary service distance is always larger than the primary. From this figure it can be observed that the potential savings vary from 65 % to 73 %, and the cost function for operating the ATMs has several plateaus where the cost remains constant for increased service distances in either direction. This is because the covering sets, \mathcal{I}_{mk}^C , are not extended evenly, but rather in increments of various lengths. This is especially true for small distances, where all distances shorter than 10 km are associated to the same objective value. This is the reasoning for selecting just one service distance and keeping it relatively short at 1km in the base case. Probably, the most interesting result one can deduce from this study is that the secondary covering distance does not have any effect before it reaches approximately 11 km. It is unrealistic to assume that the customers are willing to travel 11 km to visit an ATM. As such, the secondary service distance does not seem useful in this case, and it is thus omitted in the base case and all its variations considered in what follows.

Figure 5: Costs for different combinations of primary and secondary covering distances in km

6.1.2 Relationship between primary service distance and covering proportion

Figure 6 illustrates how the costs change when the primary covering distance (D_1^C) and the customer covering proportion in the first period ($P_{1,1}^C$) vary. Compared to the previous case (Figure 5), this analysis gives a picture of how costs are affected by increasing the proportion of customers covered. Here, the lowest cost (illustrated in blue) is less than half of the cost incurred when the covering proportion is at its highest (illustrated in red). Still, the red color illustrates potential savings of around 60% compared to the costs of operating the currently existing ATM network, showing that there is a high potential for savings with respect to operating the network as of today. Figure 6 further illustrates that the chosen service distance does not influence the optimal objective values to a large extent. Longer service distances are also unrealistic. In conclusion, the proportion of customers covered influences the solution much more than the service distance, so the chosen solution should be based on what can be regarded as a reasonable coverage proportion.

Figure 6: Costs when varying service distance and covering proportion.

In particular, the solutions span from a potential saving of 53.5 %, when the covering proportion is close to its limit, and up to potential savings of 80 %. These large potential savings, even for high covering proportions, are due to several factors. One factor that seems to be very important is that, as many ATMs are not contributing to coverage, they can be decommissioned without affecting the covering proportion. Furthermore, customer coverage is assumed to decline by 5% during the planning horizon, reducing the operating costs every year. Last, some of the ATMs are generating a positive operating profit, which is not taken into account in the current operating costs.

6.1.3 Optimized network for the base case

The optimal solution of the model for the base case gives ATM networks as shown in Figures 7 and 8 for time periods 1 and \mathcal{T} , respectively. This solution illustrates how large cities with a high density of customers are prioritized over more remote locations. This is because a higher proportion of the total customer base is covered by each individual ATM, and the remote ATMs often have higher expenses. Compared to keeping the existing ATM network configuration, the base case gives a potential reduction of 61.4 % in total operating costs for the planning horizon. Interestingly, it is optimal to open up two new locations during the planning horizon.

6.1.4 Covering forecasted turnover

The base case does not consider the need to cover the forecasted turnover (i.e. P_t^T is zero). However, covering of turnover may for some decision makers be equally important as customer

Figure 7: ATM coverage in the end of the first period of the planning horizon

Figure 8: ATM coverage at end of the planning horizon

coverage. In order to take this into consideration, this section provides results obtained by introducing turnover coverage into the base case. This is done in two ways. On the one hand, customer coverage is replaced with turnover coverage (i.e., $P_{tk}^C = 0$, and P_t^T takes different minimum turnover coverage values). The results of this case are presented in Figure 9, where the lower limits on covered turnover are illustrated with a percentage of the forecasted turnover (and varied between 85 % and 100 %). On the other hand, both customer coverage and turnover coverage are considered simultaneously (i.e. both P_{t1}^C and P_t^T vary). Similarly, the results of this case are presented in Figure 10 where, in addition to varying P_t^T , the first degree covering criterion limits are varied between 85 % and 94 %.

Figure 9: Costs with varying covered forecasted turnover

As illustrated by Figure 9, even full coverage of the forecasted turnover gives potential savings of about 25 % compared to keeping the existing ATM network. This is a direct consequence of the assumed decline during the planning horizon and illustrates the effect on the solution of the proportion of future turnover covered. Furthermore, the costs drop significantly when reducing the minimum turnover that must be covered by a modest 5 %, probably because remote ATMs which usually cover a relatively small amount of the total demand are the ones terminated first. In addition, Figure 10 shows again the importance of the covering criteria, both for customer coverage and forecasted turnover, and how they affect the cost. These results highlight the importance of being able to present several solutions to the decision maker.

Figure 10: Costs related to varying customer coverage and covered turnover

6.1.5 Sensitivity analysis of ATM revenues

To analyze the impact of ATM revenues in the problem, we have performed a sensitivity analysis. However, since no results on individual ATM locations can be shown, the discussion has been kept on a more general level. We conducted two types of sensitivity analyses: one where only the revenues of the new ATM locations are varied and one where the revenues to all ATM locations are varied. All revenues in consideration are varied with the same proportion relative to its base value. Revenues are varied instead of costs because the revenues only consist of variable elements. Furthermore, it is the profit or loss in each time period that is important, not the absolute value of the costs. The sensitivity analysis showed that the value of the profit had nearly no effect on the optimal solutions. Varying the profits of the new ATMs had no effect on the optimal solution at all, with two new ATMs opened up and closed down in the same preceding time periods. This is probably a result of the high initial customer covering proportion set. Since new ATMs need to be installed at some time in the network, it is better to install them on new locations and close down some locations that do not contribute as much to the coverage. If a lower customer covering proportion was set in the base case, no new ATM location would be opened. In addition, varying the operating profits of all the ATMs had little effect on the optimal solution. Only some small changes are observed. Most notably is that a few ATMs that are kept open in the beginning in the base case will be closed down in instances with operating profits. This implies that more ATMs than strictly needed to comply with the covering requirements are kept open.

6.2 Multi-objective results

This section analyzes the results obtained by applying the multi-objective techniques presented in Section 4 to the proposed mathematical model with the three objective functions described in Section 3.3. The purpose is to illustrate the performance related to Pareto optimality when considering the cost, the geographical coverage, and the coverage of forecasted turnover of the different multi-objective methods. For this purpose, the same set of 4,800 different weight configurations are used in all the experiments. Ideally, each weight configuration, leading to one single run of the algorithm, would provide a different point of the Pareto frontier. However, this will not always be the case, since the same solution may be found by two or more weight configurations. As it will be shown in what follows, different methods will provide different numbers of efficient solutions.

Weighted sum

The weighted sum method provides a sufficient condition for Pareto optimality, and thus the dots presented in Figure 11 are guaranteed to be part of the Pareto frontier. Even though 4,800 different runs are executed, only 777 unique solutions are obtained. It must be noted that this is a quite reduced number of solutions, indicating that the same solution is frequently obtained with different weight configurations. This method does not provide a wide range of cheap solutions, corresponding to low turnover and cover values; however, with a rather small cost increase, turnover and cover values can be improved significantly in several different ways, and there is a relatively high density of quite expensive solutions (close to 100%), providing also, as expected, very high turnover and cover values (very close to 100% as well).

Figure 11: Approximation of the Pareto efficient frontier with the weighted sum method

Archimedean goal programming

Even though Archimedean goal programming might result in non-Pareto optimal points, and thus its solutions cannot be guaranteed to be efficient, the shape of the approximated Pareto frontier obtained is nearly identical to the one obtained from the execution of the weighted sum method. Again, a relative small number of unique solutions, 750, are generated, and most of them coincide with those depicted in Figure 11.

Modified weighted Tchebycheff

Minimizing the modified weighted Tchebycheff function (39) is both necessary and sufficient for Pareto optimality for discrete problems, such as the problem approached in this paper. The results obtained for this method are shown in Figure 12. It is interesting to note that it returns a relatively high number of unique solutions, 1734, compared to the weighted sum method and goal programming, which provide less than half of those. This is important, since it allows to obtain a denser Pareto front. In comparison with the solutions shown in Figure 11, it can be observed that the Pareto front provided by the modified weighted Tchebycheff method is much denser in the area with reduced cost solutions, generating many different cheap solutions with reasonable cover and turnover values; however, it seems no solution with a cost higher than 60% is generated, whereas this did not happen to the weighted sum method, which produced efficient solutions with costs close to 100% (and thus very good turnover and cover values). As a result, one could decide to use the weighted sum method if one is more interested in the high cost/high cover and turnover part of the Pareto front, and the modified weighted Tchebycheff method if one prefers a wide variety of cheap solutions with reasonable cover and turnover values to choose from.

Figure 12: Approximation of the Pareto efficient frontier with the modified Tchebycheff method

Description of the Pareto optimal frontier

From the previous results, it is evident that the gradient to the Pareto optimal frontier is increasing with increasing relative weights on the two forms of covering considered in the multi-objective formulation of the problem. As such, it is relatively cheap to increase coverage up to around a cost level of 30-40%. From this point and up to the maximum possible coverage of customers and turnover, increasing the network's average coverage becomes increasingly expensive. As the two types of coverage are related to each other, an increase in one will most probably result in an increase in the other. However, since many ATMs in the existing network can be decommissioned while still keeping the current customer coverage according to the model, high values of customer coverage can still result in a relatively low coverage of turnover. Therefore, the weight put on turnover coverage must be very high in relation to the other two objective functions to obtain its maximum value.

7 Concluding remarks

Effective operations in the banking industry have been becoming increasingly important during the last years, mainly due to higher competition and lower profit margins. In addition, the demand of cash from the population has been decreasing, and thus the need of ATMs has also varied significantly, creating the need of re-evaluating certain strategic decisions taken in the past. In this context, the main contribution of our work is a multi-objective linear integer programming model for a new strategic location problem in the banking industry related to the re-design and re-optimization of an existing ATM network. For this real problem we have also developed a case study with real data that represents an additional and interesting contribution to the literature. The computational results showed that there is a high potential for achieving important cost savings while not decreasing significantly the geographical or turnover coverage.

When the coverage of customers or turnover is close to its potential, the costs increase more rapidly than for lower values of coverage. Consequently, with good coverage proportions between 85-90%, high cost reductions of more than 70% of the total cost reduction potential can be achieved. In addition, we observed that, due to the wide geographical area considered, the sets of ATM locations that cover each municipality center do not change much when increasing the service distance.

From the multi-objective study performed we observed that the modified weighted Tchebycheff method showed the best general performance, even though it required the highest computational effort. If the execution time is an issue, the weighted sum method should be used instead. In any case, the Pareto optimal frontier obtained by any of these methods should be the basis for the decision maker to select a reasonable solution to be implemented for the redesign of the ATM network.

There are several future research lines that could continue this work. Probably, the most interesting one regards the inclusion of stochasticity in the model, which could be modelled by the use of different scenarios associated to different possible realizations of future turnover, revenues and costs. Another research line could be trying to improve the way new potential locations

for ATMs are found; this could be done by solving a mathematical model aimed at finding the best locations for capturing the demand flows associated to the customers. Finally, alternative multi-objective methods could also be investigated to try to build denser Pareto frontiers.

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